

SIGNIFICANCE OF TRADITIONS IN RITUAL APPEARANCE IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THE SURKHANDARYO DANCE SCHOOL

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Annotation: In this article, the history of Surkhan oasis dance art, which is a part of Uzbek national dance art, and local aspects related to it are interpreted. An analysis of traditional dance masterpieces staged by master artists, the uniqueness of Khorezm, Bukhara and Fergana dance schools, were presented. In the second millennium BC, a number of independent cities, as well as states such as Khorezm, Sugdiyana, Bactria, were formed in Central Asia. The holy book of Zoroastrian religion “Avesta” contains information about the following countries. The article also contains a description of folk dances and dances of the Surkhan village. Surkhan dances show people’s customs, folk games, and show people’s joy, strength, dexterity, bravery, enthusiasm and courage are depicted in these dances.

Key words: dance, art, history, style, technology, meditation, tradition, music, melody, song, creativity.

1. Introduction

In dance, human intuition, thoughts, inner experiences, emotions are expressed not by speech, but by gestures. Dance began to be born with the appearance of mankind. In the primitive community system, people expressed their status with actions without being able to speak with language. During this period, the dance represented the labor process, the movement of animals, and the state of battle, while during the period of slavery, it represented manners. Wealthy people danced at the balls of that time. Their dances were based on folk dances.

Later, with the demands of life, the meaning of art changed. In this place, a new theme, new characters, new customs appeared in the choreography. Such dances were born that gave people joy and pleasure. For example, lively, heroic, humorous, passionate, public, individual dances reveal the image of contemporaries. The dances of one nation are very different from those of another. Even the dances of one region are not at all similar to another. This is in the diversity of people’s character, way of life and lifestyle.

In the second millennium BC, a number of independent cities, as well as states such as Khorezm, Sugdiyana, Bactria, were formed in Central Asia. The holy book of Zoroastrian religion “Avesta” contains information about the following countries:

Parkona – Fergana region.

Sugdiyana – Areas with abundant irrigated land around the Zarafshan River.

Khorezm – Lands downstream of the Amudarya River.

Parfiyona – The lands of Turkmenistan near the Caspian Sea and the Herat region of Afghanistan.

Margiyona – The Marv region of Turkmenistan and the lands downstream of the Mughrab River.

Bactria is the northern regions of Afghanistan, the region near the Amudarya River in Tajikistan, and the Surkhandarya region of Uzbekistan.

High culture and art flourished in the above-mentioned regions since ancient times. As a result of the development of various handicrafts in the cities and prosperity in the life of the

population, singers, musicians and dancers took part in family weddings and ceremonies. This also led to the development of these given areas of art.

Under the influence of the crisis of centuries, opposition of kings, anger of tyrant rulers, wars and quarrels, talented painters, clowns, actors, sculptors and dance masters who matured in the centers of culture such as Bactria, Sugdiyana, and Khorezm left for countries where these arts were not under pressure. The artists who stayed in their country lived in mountain villages and created “Artist Villages” similar to Darkh villages, and these villages played an important role in the preservation of our ancient art.

There are such villages in Surkhandarya region as well. “Katariguzar” village in Boysun district, “Katta Vakhshivor” and “Kichik Vakhshivor” villages in Altinsoy district, “Zevar” village in Sariosiya district, “Sina” and “Ushor” villages in Denov district have long been recognized as villages of artists, and this tradition continues to this day, rare masterpieces of our art have reached our time.

2. Research methodology

In dance, human intuition, thoughts, inner experiences, emotions are expressed not by speech, but by gestures. Dance began to be born with the appearance of mankind. In the primitive community system, people expressed their status with actions without being able to speak with language. During this period, the dance represented the labor process, the movement of animals, and the state of battle, while during the period of slavery, it represented manners.

In the speech of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev at the “Lazgi” folk festival (26.04.2022), he said: “It is known that every nation is rightly proud of its cultural heritage, which has been formed and polished over many centuries and passed from generation to generation. In this sense, the rich and colorful Uzbek dance art, which is considered to be our great spiritual treasure, is of great importance as it embodies the elegance and beauty of our nation, noble dreams and aspirations. Deep study of the history of our national dance art, its specific features and widespread promotion among young people are urgent issues today”. Presidential decree-3920 dated August 2, 2018 “On measures for innovative development of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, PD-4038 dated November 21, 2018 “On approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, PD-4584 dated February 4, 2020 “On measures for the further development of the national art of dance”, PD-4585 of February 4, 2020 “On measures to fundamentally improve the system of training highly qualified personnel in the field of dance art and further develop its scientific potential” and to this field of activity the research of this article serves to a certain extent the implementation of the tasks defined in other normative legal documents.

3. Analysis of literature on the topic

The study of the history of the dance art of the people of the Surkhan oasis is primarily related to the ethnography of the oasis. For this reason, in the coverage of the theme of the dance art of the oasis as a part of social and household life, “History and culture of Uzbekistan, - Ethnography of Surkhon Darya” [2] “Surkhon Darya ethnographic space” [3], “Ceremonial folklore of the Uzbek people” [4], “Surkhan is the history of intangible culture of the inhabitants of the oasis” [5], “History of the formation and development of the art of bakhshilik in Uzbekistan” [6], “Ethnography of the Harduris” [7], “Surkhan dance schools” [8] and “Surkhandarya folk seasonal dances” [9] we used the literature, on this basis we tried to reveal the content of the topic.

In preparing the article, we used comparative-analytical, observational, analytical, classification and retrospective methods.

4. Analysis and results

The Surkhan oasis, located in the south of Uzbekistan, has been considered one of the cradles of mankind since ancient times. The extreme nationalism of the dance art of the Surkhan oasis, as well as the fact that the above-mentioned direction was accepted by the local leaders in the Soviet ideology as an antiquated style due to the uniqueness of the folk art, also contributed to the development of the Surkhandarya dance style, preserving its various seasonal, ceremonial, customs and traditions interfered with the construction and had a negative impact on its development.

Dances of the Surkhan oasis came to the attention of the art community only after the “Shalola” ensemble group from Boysun district of the mountain region took part in the 8th Surkhan Mountain Folklore Festival in 1975, in Zakopane, Poland and won the “Silver Axe” prize. After that and nowadays, Surkhan dance movements are expressed in the movements of many folk groups in our Republic and dancers who dance to songs performed in Surkhan Darya-Kashkadarya singing style. The art of dance lives with its creative performers. Old people who were expert performers of ancient dances of Surkhan oasis have passed away. However, Surkhan dances did not disappear completely. The style of the Surkhan dance school and the dances belonging to the school, and the depiction of the various movements in the dances, require more scientific research. In writing this short thesis, we mainly used the materials collected in the “Boysun” folklore ethnographic ensemble at the Central House of Culture of the Boysun district. At this point, we found it permissible to dwell on the costumes of dancers and their unique national features.

Uzbek women’s everyday and festive clothes are very stylish, different and colorful. Every region of our republic has its own costumes created over centuries in accordance with nature, climate and living conditions. Surkhandarya region is not an exception. Surkhandarya women usually choose brightly colored, large patterned fabrics for their dresses. Other clothes, which were made in a narrower shape for young girls, and in a wider shape for women, vests worn over the dress, loyam (the name of apparel), various footwear, headscarves, jewelry, were the main components of Surkhandarya women’s clothing. The clothes worn by women in everyday life are made of gray, olacha, janda, khadi fabrics woven by local weavers. For women’s dresses and skirts made of semi-silk fabrics, vanoras, abrishim, silk, satin and khan satin, usually red, light green, yellow, light yellow colors were chosen.

Two or one-way decoration is sewn from the collar to the hem of the shirt. In addition, the hem of the shirt has a one-inch wide patterned decoration.

A similar decoration is sewn on the hem of the shirt. Women’s lozim (the name of the clothes like trousers) is narrow, and a chiroz sewn on a belt or a needle is placed on the lozim’s hem. Above the chiroz, a one or a half inch wide ornament is sewn. Girls’ body is cut narrower. Over the shirt, they usually wore “sleeveless vest” and “short vest”. The collars, hems and hems of nimchas and kamzils are decorated with patterns. Women used different colored cotton shawls in their daily life. In festivals and ceremonies, the king’s shawls are usually woven from silk - chorsi, doka, farangi, gijim, flower shawl shawl, large shawl and silk shawls.

Among the headdresses, the “beaded cap” decorated with beads and embroidered with a decorative headdress, the “velvet cap” made of plain velvet are common. The headdress of bell women belonging to the nomadic clan of Uzbeks living in the Surkhandarya region is “puta”, which is made of different colored laces. In everyday life, women used shoes made of leather called “popish” and “bachki takhsi”. On holidays and ceremonies, they are usually covered with shawls woven from silk: chorsi, gauze farangi, gijim, floral scarf, large shawl, silk scarf. Among the headdresses, caps are decorated with beads and “beaded cap” with a decorative headdress, and “velvet cap” made of plain velvet are common. “Kovush”, “Amirkon Kovush”, “Gharch Kovush”, “Amirkon Makhshi” were used in holidays and ceremonies.

Various rituals and traditional holidays of folklore are colorful and they mark the seasons of the year. This process cannot be imagined without songs and dances. As we mentioned above, it is true to associate the period of origin of dances with hunting, which occurred during the Eneolithic

(new stone) period, followed by animal farming. The works performed by human hands and activities since ancient times are directly related to the organic cycle of the seasons. As a result, people invented various rituals, customs, traditions and even seasonal events. All of them are based on work and, of course, playful (dance) movements. As a result, complementary seasonal dances emerged. In the course of this study, we came across the concept of ritual directly. Because the seasonal dances that are the subject of our research are actually widely performed in seasonal ceremonies. For this reason, in the study of seasonal dances, it was necessary to refer to them as seasonal ritual dances in some cases. For example, in connection with the arrival of spring, dance movements such as “The sun came out”, “Stork”, “Boychechak”, “Swallow”, “Eagle” were performed. “Sumalak” and “Gulyor” are performed with seasonal dances. These beautiful and great celebrations were created on the basis of the polytheistic concepts of our most ancient ancestors, including beliefs about the universe, the sun and the earth. 4-5 thousand years ago, our ancestors considered the sun to be the greatest power, the source of life, the source of light and heat and called it held special ceremonies.

Boysun’s tune “Mavrigi” also has a power that restrains unruly emotions. When the melody is played in rhythm, the circle beats are accented every other count. While the movement of the dance is gentle in the first count, the dancer moves sharply at the end of the second count. In general, all the movements in the dance “Boysun Mavrigi” are performed in two contradictory numbers. It is clear that “Boysun Mavrigi” has been preserved intact since ancient times. This can be understood from the fact that this dance was performed in ancient rituals and that there is an interpretation of the connection of man with divine forces in heaven and earth, based on the movements, gestures in the movements, the dancer’s keeping a serious facial expression during the performance. In ancient times, every movement and every gesture expressed concepts that could be understood by the audience without words. That is, the role of movement and gesture was very actively involved in the expression of thought. “Mavrigi”, a masterpiece of ancient dance art, is performed as a one-man show and is still performed at weddings and festivals in the city of Boysun. The dance lasts 25-30 minutes, the musicians play the tune repeatedly and the dances alternate.

If we pay attention to Surkhan dances, the main dances reflect ritual scenes. Performing ritual dances requires great skill and responsibility from the dancer. Because it is difficult to express the theme of the dance, the reality of the dance with ritual movements. Therefore, in this topic, we found it necessary to analyze several Surkhan ritual dances, which gained importance in the establishment of the Surkhan dance school.

I. “CHANKOVUZ” DANCE. Chankovuz is the oldest unique musical instrument of the Turkic people. Mostly women danced to the tune of Chankovuz. Like the circle method, the chankovuz method also has an oral tone. During the teaching of the dances performed in Chankovuz, they used the melody and count. Below we will consider the most commonly used tunes in chankovuz dances and the image of the dance moves to these tunes. This dance is performed by a group of at least 8 dancers.

First position of movement: the figure is straight and proud, the dancers with a knot on their head have their arms close to the elbows on both sides, the wrists are bent to the side, and the palms are directed down. A group of dancers from both sides of the stage, keeping their right feet 10-15 cm from the floor in line with the melody rising, and the left foot is lifted from the ground, taking a small step forward, they meet in the center of the stage and sit in a tight row. In this case, the dancers come to the stage in 16 counts.

Second position of movement: without breaking the row of dancers, without moving the two dancers in the middle, the row turns around its axis one time in 8 counts, and again they are placed in a wider row.

Third position of the movement: The dancers standing in a line perform this movement while standing. In the first 2 counts, the right leg is extended forward and the shoulder is raised twice. In the second 2 counts, the head is shaken by making a “slanted neck” twice. The same actions are fully performed on the left side. A total of 12 movements are performed.

Fourth position of movement: This action begins in the middle of the scene. One side of the two rows of dancers facing each other, without changing the position of their left hand, stretches their right arm to the side at shoulder level, palms facing up, and moves to the right in 4 counts, the second row of dancers, in 4 counts, with their right hand down, their left arm extended to the left at shoulder level, and the left moves from side to side, and after the lines “sweep” past each other, they take the shape of a semicircle on the stage.

Fifth position of movement: the dancers raise their hands to shoulder height and perform the “rolling up the sleeves” movement 4 times in 4 counts.

Sixth position of movement: Dancers, while standing in 4 counts, spread their arms shoulder-width apart, turn to the right by “shrugging” their shoulders, and make a “slanted neck” movement. In another count of four, they perform the same movements on the left side one complete time.

Seventh position of movement: Dancers are in a row, holding two hands in front of the chest, palms facing down. The dancers move forward while the right hand is raised higher, the left hand lower to the right, and the same movement is made to the left. The movement is performed in 6 counts.

Eighth position of movement: Dancers standing in a row remove their knots from their heads in 2 counts, sit on the left knee and put their knots on the floor.

Ninth movement position: Dancers spread the four corners of their knot on the floor in 4 counts.

Tenth movement position: in 12 counts, the dancers delicately remove the cotton from the knot, twist it, and in another 4 counts, they transfer the cotton package to the wrist of their left hand and prepare to spin the yarn in the ball.

Eleventh movement position: Dancers touch the ball to their right knees in 8 counts, rotate the ball, extend their hands forward with their palms facing down, and do two more shrugs in 2 counts.

Twelfth position of movement: while standing up, the dancers split into two sides, bend slightly to the left with their hands raised high, and perform the movement of wrapping the thread around the ball in 4 counts. In another 4 counts, the figure is slightly bent to the right, and the string on the ball is lengthened again, and in this process the dancers take the shape of a semicircle.

Thirteenth position of movement: 2 of the dancers in a semicircle on the net, with their hands raised high, rotate with their legs in a pole movement, cross in front of each other, and sit diagonally on the stage. The rest of the couples repeat the same movement and take a diagonal position on the stage. All these movements are performed in 16 counts.

Fourteenth position of movement: the first pair of dancers, located diagonally behind, turn the ball, bend slightly with their arms raised high, and with their left hand they press the braided hair above the waist, and go around each other together with the spinning ball. The two pairs in the middle rotate the ball while standing still, bending slightly while standing still and rotating around their axis. The fourth pair in front, while sitting in their seats, rotate the ball, stretch the right palm, sometimes up, sometimes down, and do two shrugs. All these movements are performed in 16 counts.

Fifteenth movement position: Dancers, holding a cotton roll in their left hand and a stick in their right hand, move their arms forward, moving once to the right and once to the left, until they reach their spread knots in 8 counts.

Sixteenth movement position: Dancers sit on the left knee, collect the knot with a movement corresponding to the melody, get up and fix the knot on their heads. These movements are performed in 6 counts.

Seventeenth position of movement: Dancers hold their figures proudly and move gracefully as if they are playing a turban. This action is repeated three times. In the third time, the right hand is stopped, and in this position they stand alone.

II. "KADI" DANCE. This dance is performed with the participation of 8 girls. Dancers carry a kadi (pumpkin) in their hands. The dance is performed to the tune of an unconventional musical instrument called “water pumpkin”. Pumpkin makes a sound like “guv-guv” and is heard in one rhythm.

First position of movement: the dancers hold the kadi with their right hands, and with their left hands they lift the silk scarf by the edge and hide their faces and they come onto the stage with small graceful steps one by one according to the method. This movement is performed for 16 counts.

Second position of movement: Dancers continue the movement, open their faces, hold the caddy on the right side with both hands, press their right hips and turn in a circle. This movement is performed for 8 counts.

Third position of movement: During the movement, the dancers stand in a tight circle, hold the kadis from the bottom up with two hands, and lift them up. This movement is performed in 8 counts.

The fourth is the position of movement: the dancers turn from the right shoulder and turn to face each other, raise the caddis from the bottom up, open the circle and sit in a semicircle. The movement is performed in 8 counts.

The fifth is the state of action. When the kadi is on top, the dancers deftly turn from the right shoulder and lift the kadi over the head. Then the pumpkins are lowered to the right side at waist level and raised again, and the same movements are performed on the left side. This movement is performed 4 times in 16 counts.

Sixth position of movement: Dancers hold the kadi lying on their left side, circle the kadi's mouth and rotate once in their place. These movements are performed in 8 counts. During the above movement, they march forward and line up until they play the kadi.

Seventh position of movement: Dancers stand in a row, hold the pumpkins with both hands above their heads and sit on the floor in a row.

Eighth position of movement: The dancers place the pumpkin on the floor in front of them and move their hands 4 times slowly and 4 times quickly, as if playing a gourd. 4 slow pulling movements are performed in 8 counts, 4 fast pulling movements are performed in 4 counts.

Ninth movement position: Dancers stand up nimbly from their seats, leave the caddis where they are, hold their handkerchiefs from both sides, spread them in the form of a butterfly, and retreat with their backs to the stage. This action is performed in the remaining 4 counts.

Tenth movement position: Dancers stand on their sides towards the audience and look at the audience with a scarf covering their faces. These movements are performed 2 times in 8 counts.

Eleventh position of movement: Dancers come to the kadi, spread their scarves on both sides, rotate in place with a shrug, take the kadi from the ground, lift them over the head, and place them on their right shoulders with both hands. These movements are performed in 8 counts and the dance is completed.

III. "BOYSUN MAVRIGI" DANCE:

In the "Mavrigi" dance, special respect is shown to the solo dancer. Because, since long ago, in the territory of the Surkhan oasis, if a man became famous for his some quality, bravery, he was allowed to go out and dance at weddings and ceremonies. This custom is found in the mountainous villages of Boysun, Altinsoy, Denov, and Sariosiyo districts of the Surkhan oasis. It was preserved until the 1960s. The "Mavrigi" dance is considered the most perfect of the "jazava" dances. The peculiarity of this dance is that the whole body dances according to the method due to the "lukshima" movement of the legs in it, which is not found in other male dances. This dance is very ancient, and one of the performers known to us was Azim Surnay, who lived in the village of "Avlot" of Boysun district in the 19th century. Until the 60s of the 20th century, Grandfather Haji Bolta, who lived in Boysun, performed this dance to its standard.

Until the 80s of the 20th century, the "Mavrigi" dance was performed by Ahad Boltaev, the son of grandfather Khoji Bolta, an excellent teacher with a good voice, Zikrullo Umarov and Abdukhaliil Nazarov.

Habib Umarov, Komil Rahmonov and Ismail Jumaev, members of the folk-ethnographic ensemble "Boysun" have been performing this dance since 1986.

The difference between "Boysun mavrigi" dance and other masculine dances is that during the performance of this dance, the dancer relaxes all the muscles in his body without strengthening

them. In addition to the precise performance of the dance movements, the body part, especially the chest and shoulders, vibrate between beats. The dancer's head should be swaying separately, and the face should have a thoughtful and serious expression until the dance begins and ends. As if the whole world is moving together with the dancer, the dancer should be in a position to listen to his inner world.

“Boysun Mavrigi” also has a power that restrains unruly emotions. The dance lasts 25-30 minutes, the musicians play the tune repeatedly and the dancers alternate.

First position of movement: the dancer proudly walks in a circle and stops in the middle of the stage and listens to the melody. This movement is performed in 8 beats.

Second position of movement: Music corresponding to the circle method begins. In the first 2 counts, the dancer claps his hands as if to shake off the dust from his palms, and in the second 2 counts, the dancer acts as if he is adjusting the jelak knot on the left side of his belt. In the third 2 counts, the dancer moves as if to adjust the right side of the belt around the waist. In the next 8 counts, the dancer takes off the headdress and places it back on the head. There are three main types of headbutts:

1. “Bodicha”. The cap is worn up to the brow.
2. “Putting a dol”. The cap is set to one side.
3. “Havoyi”. The cap is placed on the back of the head.

During these movements, the dancer moves his whole body with the help of his legs. In the first 2 of the next 8 counts, the dancer curls the wrist with the right hand and the left hand. In the second 2 counts, the left hand moves as if the right wrist is bent.

In the third 2 counts, he stretches his arms forward to the left and swings them to the left, as if breaking himself, and in the fourth 2 counts he swings his arms forward to the right. During these movements, the dancer puts his feet shoulder-width apart, without leaving the tip of his feet on the ground, only raises and lowers his heels to the tune, moves his body like a dancer, and his whole body shakes from top to bottom, and his head shakes from side to side. This vibration is performed very naturally.

Third movement position: Leg movement: On each count, the right leg is bent at the knee and raised to the knee, and on the second count, the heel is placed on the floor. The left leg is slightly raised from the ground and moves upwards in two steps on the first count, giving the opportunity for full body movement. This movement is called “gajir landed”.

Arm movement: Arms are shoulder-width apart. The fingers are held together and the tips of the fingers are pointing downwards. In the second count, the hands are raised above the head in a vibrating movement, and at that time the palm rotates around the wrist and points to the sky with the fingertips.

This movement resembles the flapping of a bird's wings. The dancer performs the above movement by turning to the left in the first 2 counts, turning the whole body backwards in the second 2 counts, turning to the left again in the third 2 counts, and performing the movement to the right in the fourth 2 counts. In the next 8 counts, he returns exactly what he did before. But in these 8 counts, the dancer rotates in place from left to right.

Fourth position of movement: the half climax of the melody “Mavrigi” begins. In this part, the hand movement changes slightly, in the first 2 counts, the right arm is bent at the elbow, the elbow is raised to the level of the shoulder, and the fingertips are directed to the sky. The left arm is also bent at the elbow, the elbow is to the left, the hand is across the chest, and the fingertips are directed to the elbow of the right hand. In the second 2 counts, the same movement is performed with the left hand on the left shoulder. The dancer performs this movement alternately on the right shoulder and on the left shoulder in both counts, forming a big circle on the stage and stops at the front of the stage. The movement is performed in 16 counts.

Fifth position of movement: Both arms are extended forward with the elbows touching the elbows, the elbows bent and the palms facing down. The trunk is slightly thrown back, the head and body swing freely to the side, and the hands are dexterously stretched forward in this position. This movement is repeated 4 times, the dancer walks with his back facing the audience and goes to the

center of the stage in 8 counts. On the second 8 count, the same movement is repeated, only with the palms facing up, and this movement is repeated four times, bringing the dancer to the front of the stage.

Sixth position of movement: It is performed in 16 counts. In this part, which is the climax of the tune, the dancer stretches his arm forward and bends at the elbow, kneels in the first 2 counts while holding the left hand with the right hand, and the right elbow with the left hand moves with the action “tulganma”. In the third 2 counts, he turns his body to the right and repeats this movement. In the fourth 2 counts, he throws his body back and performs this movement looking straight. These movements are performed in 8 times in total. In the next 8 beats, without changing the sitting position, the dancer holds both arms parallel and extends them forward and upward at 45° relative to the body. Swinging the whole body with the palms bent high and pointing straight in the first 2 counts, turns to the left in the second 2 counts, turns to the right in the third 2 counts, bend the body slightly forward and move straight, and in the fourth 2 counts stands up.

Seventh position of movement: This movement position is performed in 16-count splits. The dancer keeps his figure straight, spreads his arms to the sides at shoulder length, bends the elbow at a right angle, closes his fingers, leaving only the index finger open, and in the first eight counts moves to the left side and comes back to the position. In the second 8 counts, he makes the same movements to the right side and returns to his place.

Eighth position of movement: the left hand is stretched on the waist, in one count of every two counts, the right and left hands are on the waist, and in two counts, the whole body swings the right hand twice, the hand is raised above the head with the palm facing outwards. Performing this movement, the dancer makes a big circle around the stage and comes to the center of the stage. This position is also performed in 16 counts.

Ninth movement position: This position is performed in 16 counts. The movements are divided into two parts and consist of two different movements: In the first part, the dancer puts both hands on the waist in 8 beats. The figure is thrown back and the chest comes. He shakes his head to the tune.

The footwork is in the “Ghajir kondi” method, and the dancer dances backwards, facing the audience. Backstroke is performed for 8 counts. The second part of the movement is also performed in 8 counts. The dancer raises both hands above the head, parallel, palms down towards the head, puts the fingers of the left palm on top of the right palm, uses the leg in the style of “ghajir kondi” (but increasing the leg movements), the whole body swings strongly to both sides, and moves towards the front of the stage.

Tenth movement position: in 8 beats, the dancer pulls his left hand above the waist, raises his right elbow to the side at shoulder level, bends his elbow and points to the sky with his thumb, turns his head proudly, and ends the dance by looking at the tip of his finger.

Conclusions and suggestions

The rich and colorful folklore heritage of the people of Uzbekistan is closely related to the diversity of its ethnic composition and the fact that the path of historical development passed between two rivers in Central Asia, one of the centers of the world civilization. Because the area between Amudarya and Syrdarya served as a crossroad in the great migrations of peoples and the rise and development of various political, cultural and economic relations since ancient times. In this regard, it is enough to remember that the Great Silk Road almost completely crossed this area. On the other hand, it is natural that economic, political and cultural development took place wherever the trade routes passed.

The important place in the history and development of ethnic groups and states that appeared in the region of Central Asia, including between two rivers, is determined by the fact that this region is located in favorable conditions in all respects. The Uzbek people are made up of three major ethnic groups: the Korlik, Kipchak and Oghuz tribes. As a result of their mutual union, the nucleus of today’s Uzbek people appeared.

It is known that the three tribal associations play an important role in the formation of Turkic peoples in other regions as well. The same processes are clearly visible in folk oral poetic creation. In particular, folklore, folk music, folk theater (performance art), folk games (dance), folk fine and practical decorative arts, folk architecture, and similar types of creative works of traditional material and non-material culture related to the artistic and creative practical activities of the people are more obvious. For this reason, the Uzbek people have close ties with other Turkic brothers and neighbors living next to each other. They have a lot in common. The Uzbek ethnos literally created a rich cultural heritage. In order to study dances of the Surkhandarya region, it is necessary to organize folklore expeditions on a large scale throughout the Oasis:

- It is necessary to study the scientific literature and manuscripts created to date on the topic and publish scientific articles and sources based on the results.

- In the course of the expedition organized in Surkhandarya, conducting conversations with Surkhan connoisseurs and representatives of the older generation who know national games and dances. Publication of scientific articles on the results;

- It is desirable to process the collected materials, write a description of the unique choreographic movements of seasonal dances, analyze, classify, and clarify the basics of the Surkhan school based on the results.

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